

Attributes of positive user experience and the relation to product type and time

Raeseong Kang¹
raekang@unist.ac.kr

Hyunkyung Kim¹
hkkim@unist.ac.kr

Chajoong Kim¹
cjkim@unist.ac.kr

¹Ulsan National Institute
of Science and
Technology, South Korea

Abstract Since user-centered design came to the forefront, user research has been treated as almost essential in product development process but utilized in limitation in spite of its importance. This is because traditional user study methods are time-consuming. Therefore, this study attempts to make an empirical interaction model, User Experience Attributes (UXA) in which how user experience with product or service interacts with product type and usage stage is shown. To achieve this goal, we firstly redefined attributes of positive user experience through literature review. Five attributes of positive user experience were created: sensory, instrumental, episodic, value and symbolic experiences. A mobile-based questionnaire was developed to figure out what kind of products are related to positive user experience, why they loved the product, and how positive user experience changed over time. 102 respondents participated in the survey. The results indicate that the importance of five attributes varied depending upon product type and product usage stage. The findings from the study provide an empirical interaction model showing the relation between positive user experiences, product type and usage stage with design practitioners. If it is considered in the product development process, it could reduce time and cost compared with traditional user study methods.

Keywords *User experience, Product type, Usage stage, User-centered design*

Introduction

Since user-centered design came to the forefront, user research has been treated as almost essential in product development process but utilized in limitation in spite of its importance (Lew, 2011). This situation is due to the limitations that user study methods have: 1) traditional user research methods require too much time and resources to prepare, conduct and analyze, and 2) users' needs and wishes identified from several studies cannot actually cover all the different kinds of users considering their characteristics and background knowledge (Kramer, Noronha, & Vergo, 2000; Spinuzzi, 2005). Since market is rapidly changing nowadays, those limitations are more and more critical to design practitioners. As a result, it is very challenging to carry out in-depth user research with existing user research methods. Considering these circumstances, we believe that an empirical interaction model showing how products (or services) interact with users could help design practitioners easily cope with volatile market situations instead of time-consuming and costly traditional user research.

As a try of creating an empirical model, an empirical model in our previous study (Kim & Christiaans, 2012; Kim, 2014) was developed. The focus was on the interaction between user characteristics, product types and negative product experience. The study revealed that negative user experience results mostly from the lack of instrumental value of a product and also negative user experience is rather universal

among people less depending on user characteristics. From the findings only it was not possible to draw a holistic picture of the relationship between product type, user characteristics and user experience. Considering the characteristics of positive product experience (i.e. the reasons people love to use their product), it seems that not only instrumental value but also aesthetic, personal and social values play an important role. In addition to that, usage period of product may influence positive user experience because product attachment is somehow influenced by time (Karapanos, Zimmerman, Forlizzi, & Martens, 2010). Therefore, this study as the first step to complete a holistic picture of user experience aims to 1) redefine positive user experience, 2) to empirically investigate how positive user experiences are related to product type in terms of the redefined user experience, and 3) to explore the influence of product usage period to positive user experience.

What is user experience?

One of the field that the concept of user experience or user-centered design was firstly introduced was human-computer interaction. According to Moggridge (2007), thanks to researchers' effort for ordinary people to use digital technology easier, nowadays' user can control their devices friendly without professional knowledge about programming (as cited in Wright & McCarthy, 2010). Those efforts about user-centered design were soon become a concept focusing on not just usability of technologies but how the users have

good experience (Wright & McCarthy, 2010), but the question was how the good experience could be made.

Hassenzahl (2008) tried to find the origins of UX at the level of personal achievement, and there are two kinds of personal achievements: 'do-goals' and 'be-goals'. Do-goals (pragmatic quality) facilitates fulfillment of be-goals (hedonic goals), and those hedonic attributes hold the key of experience. Consequently, he defined good UX as a result of fulfilled human needs, which are required to achieve be-goals: being autonomous, competent, related to other, simulated and popular.

Although user experience has been defined by International Standard Organization as "person's perceptions and responses resulting from the use and/or anticipated use of a product, system or service," (2010) attributes of user experience have been differently understood among disciplines because each one has their own perception on the term. For instance, Rafaeli and Vinal-Yavets (2004), an ergonomist and behavioral psychologist, suggested three components of user experience as *Instrumentality*, *Aesthetics*, and *Symbolism* of an artifact. Desmet (2007), a design researcher, classified product experience as *Aesthetic Experience*, *Attribution of Meaning* and *Emotional Experience*. Those two categorizations are similar in a sense that both emphasized experiences of aesthetics and meaning. However, in the former it stands for associational meaning, symbolic meaning attributed by relationship with others, while in the latter it is more about personal attachments to product. *Emotional Experience* in Desmet's classification stands for emotional assessment by a user, and it can be made without user's awareness. Comparing to Rafaeli's study which focused on the elements arousing user experiences, Desmet's study had their point on types of consequential experiences, thus Desmet classified *emotional response* as independent type of user experience. On the other hand, *Instrumentality* is a type of human-product interaction in Desmet's study, whereas Rafaeli classified it as one of the dimensions that makes product experience of the user.

In the field of psychology, Jordan (1999) attempted to consider positive user experience as pleasure. According to his theory, pleasure is caused by operation of sensory organs (*Physio-pleasure*), social interaction (*Socio-pleasure*), cognitive issues (*Psycho-pleasure*), and personal aspiration (*Ideo-pleasure*). Hassenzahl (2003), designer and applied psychologist, however, distinguished user experience in terms of two perspectives based on people's quality perceptions: *pragmatic* and *hedonic*. Pragmatic attribute regards instrumental goal of products, and hedonic attribute considers users' psychological goodness. The two categories are not exactly matched with Jordan's classification, but Jordan's model tends to focus more on interactions between human and product, whereas Hassenzahl's focus is on psychological or emotional functions of products.

In another study of Hassenzahl (2006), he suggested a broader framework about facets of user experience,

and it contained not only the relationship of pragmatic-hedonic needs, but emotion and experiential aspects. He highlighted the importance of emotion in terms of experience and pointed out that designer should consider the context of emotion rather than emotion itself. In addition to that, situational and temporal background, thus experiential aspect, also help to control affective state of users according to him.

Low (2006) introduced six attributes of product character called PCA (Product Character Attributes), which comprises *Aesthetics*, *Function*, *Symbolism*, *Sexuality*, *Experiences*, and *Mediation*. *Mediation* is an attribute about associating with other people, so common understanding or relationship on a product can be categorized into this attribute. According to the paper, *Experience* also counted as an attribute, and it is aroused from cognitive and emotional traits of a product, similarly with *Psycho-pleasure* or *Emotional experience*. The concept of *Aesthetics* is similar with ones of Desmet's and Rafaeli's, or *Physio-pleasure* of Jordan's study. While *Instrumentality* in Rafaeli's study is focusing on how a product promote its goal or support users' achievement, the concept of *Function* in Low's study just matters fulfillment of user needs. *Symbolism* refers representative metaphor or primary traits of a product, so it is quite different from the *Meaning* of Desmet's study. However, *Symbolism* of Rafaeli's study can include not only *Symbolism* of Low's concept, but also *Sexuality*, which means sexual identity or personality of product.

Redefined user experience

In order to redefine dimensions of user experience based on the existing models, an affinity diagram analysis was conducted. This analysis was done with a doctoral researcher, two master students, and three undergraduate students in design major.

Components that had similarities in subjects of manifesting experiences or types of interactions were grouped together, then the groups were defined the following characteristics of its components: sensory experience, instrumental experience, episodic experience, value experience and symbolic experience (see Figure 1). This new categorization of user experience does not mean that all user experiences can be clearly distinguished and divided. Rather, they mean characteristics that cause experiences with products or services.

This model is named as User eXperience Attributes (UXA, acronymically) *and the description of each attribute is as follows:*

Instrumental experience is evoked from the experience from how easily an instrumental goal is achieved that users expect while using a product. The instrumental experience is closely associated with usability, efficiency, convenience, functionality, and practicality.

Sensory experience means, in process of using a product, experience resulting from sensorial quality that perceived by human senses. This attribute includes not only the perception of visual aesthetic

Figure 1. Comparison diagram between the existing models' and redefined user experience attributes.

but also all the sensorial perception such as auditory, tactile, olfactory, and gustatory senses.

Episodic experience refers to personal experience related to the user's memory or episode with a product. With episodic experience, a product plays a medium role in bridging between a memory or episode (e.g. a birthday gift from my boyfriend) and the user.

Value experience means experience made as a product provides a user with either values that are important to the user or values that are commonly accepted by the society the user belongs to. In other words, a user judges a product in a way how well the product meets his/her personal values or the values of the society they grew up.

Symbolic experience is generated from symbol or representation that a product socially stands for. It refers to experience that a user has when a product delivers the user to a social status or a social representation by the ownership of the product and consuming the brand of the product.

As described in the introduction, the focus was on positive user experiences since in our previous studies it was only instrumental experience that influenced negative user experiences in most cases (Kim & Christiaans, 2012). Therefore, this study empirically investigated 1) why people have positive experiences with a particular product (or service), and then identified 2) how the positive user experiences are related to the UX model. Furthermore, the study also tried to figure out 3) how the period of product usage is related to the attributes of positive user experience because time is a key factor to influence user experience (Hassenzahl & Ullrich, 2007; Karapanos et al., 2010; von Wilamowitz Moellendorff, Hassenzahl, Platz, & Wilamowitz-Moellendorff, 2006).

Method

In order to identify how the attributes of positive user experience are related to particular types of product and to figure out the interaction between the attributes and usage period of product, a mobile-based questionnaire survey was conducted.

Materials

A mobile-based questionnaire was developed to answer the research questions. Mobile-based questionnaire is useful to collect a number of data quickly within a limited period because it provides respondents with easy access through laptop computer or mobile phone. It consisted of three parts: usage period and UX, product type and UX, and Demographical information of respondent. The first part aimed to identify the relationship between the period of product usage and UX. For this, a question was formulated, how much they have experienced the product or service in terms of product lifecycle model (Cathy, 2014). Based on the model, each stage of product usage was modified into a statement to help respondent understand the question as below:

- *Unpacking: I just take the product off from its package.*
- *First use: I began to use the product or service.*
- *Ongoing use Phase 1: I am getting familiar with the product or service.*
- *Ongoing use Phase 2: I already got familiar with using this product or service.*
- *Discard/Replacement: now I am considering the product to be changed or discarded.*

The second part was for figuring out whether UXs are related to particular product types. Questions were made to ask the participants how much they agree on each of five attributes regarding the product they already mentioned in the previous question, and they were measured on five-level Likert scale. In order to make respondents better understood the notions of the attributes, detailed descriptions with relevant

examples were given before each question. For the attributes of which the given score was equal or more than '3(Neither of agree nor disagree)', an additional open-ended question was given asking why he/she had given the score. Then a question was lastly added to identify what attribute was most important among five attributes of positive product experience. After completing the questionnaire, a page asking demographical information of the respondent such as gender and age was shown.

Sample

In order to recruit as many respondents as possible, the survey was advertised through social networking services such as Facebook. A total of 102 respondents (50 males and 52 females) participated in the survey. They were all Koreans whose ages ranged from 15 to 56 years old ($M=31.47$, $SD=12.63$). 51 respondents out of 102 respondents were students, and the others were from diverse occupations such as administration officer, service provider, researchers and education provider.

Procedure

The questionnaire survey was conducted through an online platform which is called Typeform. The respondents were asked to first answer what his/her favorite product (or service). In the next page, they were asked to read each question regarding the five UXAs and mark on the five Likert scale (Strongly disagree, disagree, neither of agree nor disagree, agree, and Strongly Agree) how much they like the product because of that particular attribute. Except for the cases their mark was negative (below neutral, 3) for a certain attribute, they were asked to explain why she/he likes the product or service in details. After these questions, the respondents selected one of the five attributes, which was most important in explaining why he/she likes the product (or service).

Data analysis

Three types of data were gathered from the mobile-based questionnaire survey: the most favorite products or services, scores of each UXA on Likert scale, the most important attributes and descriptive data on the reasons they love the products or services.

All the products or services reported from the survey were grouped into 13 product categories: home appliances, consumer electronics, computer accessories, automotive products, stationaries, foods, infant products, sport products, clothes, cosmetics/beauty, home/decorations, health care products, and services. The product classification was made based on the categorization system of the biggest online shopping malls such as Amazon and EBay. Although services did not exist in the category systems of the shopping malls, it was added because service was also often reported in the survey as something the respondents liked to experience.

The scores of each UXA were averaged, and then the mean values were compared between product types as well as between the stages of usage. The most important attribute for each product type was quantitatively analyzed and its frequency was also

4 → How much have you used the product? ([Product Name])*

Following options are about stages of usage from your Purchase to Discard. Please answer what stage you are in, so far.

- A I just take the product off from its package.
- B I began to use the product or service.
- C I am getting familiar with the product or service.
- D I already got familiar with using this product or service.
- E Now I am considering the product to be changed or discarded.

Measuring Stage of Usage

5 → I like [Product Name], because of its sensory characteristics such as shape, sound, texture or touch.*

For examples:

- I like the shape and color of it.
- I am interested in the sound the product makes.
- The product gives me warm and soft feelings.

Scoring each attribute

(in case the score is 3 or higher)

11 → Please choose the most important reason why you like [Product Name].*

- A Value attributes: missions, social norms, shared values, faith or others.
- B Sensory attributes: shape, sound, touch or others.
- C Episodic attributes: memory, episodes, experiences, or others.
- D Instrumental attributes: functionality, efficiency, usability or others.
- E Symbolic attributes: brand, images, symbol, or others.
- F Other

Ranking the attributes

Figure 2. A part of the questionnaire measuring UXA.

considered in the analysis. Based on the descriptive data which contained information about why the respondents loved the products or services, sub-categories of each UXA were created by sorting in terms of similarity. Not only the most important attributes but also the other ones were taken into account to create the sub-categories of UXAs. This analysis was conducted by six undergraduate students who majored in industrial design, a master student and a doctoral researcher.

Results

Product type and positive user experience

A total of 102 products and services were reported as the most favorites and they were categorized into one of 13 product groups (Figure 3). Consumer electronics such as tablet PC, personal sound system and digital camera were most often mentioned (27%) and services

Figure 3. Percentages of The Most Favorite Products or Services in terms of product type (N=102).

and cosmetics were the second (16% respectively). The other categories took similar percentages ranging from 5% to 8%: sports (8%), computer accessories (8%), home appliances (7%), Home/decorations (6%), stationaries (5%). Others (7%) included health care product, automotive product, foods, infant products, and clothes. Product categories that had taken less than five percent were excluded in the further analysis because it would make the results biased with only a few cases.

Table 1. Positive user experience attributes and their subcategories.

User Experience Attribute	Coding	Sub-category
Sensory Experience	SE1	Perceived appearance
	SE2	Amusement in interactions
	SE3	Atmosphere/impression
	SE4	Sensorial comfort
Instrumental Experience	IE1	High functionality
	IE2	High durability
	IE3	Simplicity
	IE4	Efficiency
Episodic Experience	EE1	Gift
	EE2	Product (or service)-related episode
	EE3	Cumulated experiences
	EE4	Experience of problem solving
Value Experience	VE1	Self-administration/self-improvement
	VE2	Personal value
	VE3	Common benefit
Symbolic Experience	SyE1	Social recognition
	SyE2	Brand image or identity
	SyE3	Brand credibility
	SyE4	Sense of belonging

Sub-categories of positive user experience attributes

In consequence of clustering reasons why the respondents had positive user experiences with their product or service within each attribute, a total of 20 subcategories (four subcategories per attribute) were created as shown in Table 1. Each element of UXa somehow depends on each other rather than works independently to the overall outcome of user experience. Especially, last three attributes, Episodic experience, Value experience, and Social symbol experience could be the case in a sense that those attributes are more context-dependent than the others. Sensory, instrumental, episodic, value, and symbolic experience had each 69, 87, 39, 29 and 43 descriptive reasoning data.

Sensory Experience (see examples in Figure 4)

- **Perceived appearance (SE1)** means experience resulting from the perception of product or service appearance and color, form, materials, and texture are associated with this experience. For example, a respondent loved his Lamy safari because of the shape and texture of the fountain pen.
- **Amusement in interaction (SE2)** is about joy or satisfaction related to sensorial feedbacks that are directly or indirectly made between product or service and user. For instance, a respondent told he loved Palomino Blackwing pencil because it gave him good tactile feeling while writing or drawing.
- **Atmosphere or impression (SE3)** means secondary and consequential emotion aroused from identical or mixed sense(s) during using a product or service, and usually this mood or feeling represents characteristics of product or service itself. For instance, a respondent loved the Original Sound Track of his favorite musical because it aroused him joyful emotion.
- **Sensorial comfort (SE4)** is experienced when a user feels comfortable resulting from the interaction between product or service and user during usage without disrupted by unexpected stimuli. According to a story of a respondent she loved her bedclothes just because it delivered her deep comfort.

Instrumental Experience (see examples in Figure 5)

- **High functionality (IE1)** is experienced when a product or service performs better than the expectation of the user. The terms such as effectiveness, functional variety and usefulness belongs to this subcategory. A respondent was fond of Geforce Titan X, graphic card for PC because it incredibly enhanced graphical performance of his computer when he played a computer game.
- **High durability (IE2)** means how a product works well without failure, or how long the product lasts without any malfunction. For example, a respondent said he liked his gas boiler because it was hardly broken compared to what he had used before.

SE1 Lamy's Safari

SE2 Blackwing, a pencil

SE3 OST of a Musical

SE4 Bedclothes

Figure 4. Examples of sensory experience sub-categories.

- **Simplicity (IE3)** is about how easily users can achieve his/her goal during the usage of a product or a service. Ease to use such as functional simplification can explain this subcategory. For instance, a respondent mentioned that her Aeropress machine is easy to make brewed coffee and functionally simple.
- **Efficiency (IE4)** is about how well a product or a service works efficiently in terms of users' efforts, time or economical cost. It is distinguished from high functionality in a sense that functionality is about how well product or service achieves instrumental goals. Usually, efficiency is more related to the amount of a resource necessary to achieve one task compared to functionality. A respondent selected her coffee machine called Kitchen Art Plus because the machine helped her to save time in case of boiling water.

Episodic Experience (see examples in Figure 6)

- **Extrinsic meaning (EE1)** means an experience to be evoked by other people. The typical example is gift and a person has a positive user experience with a product or a service when it is given by somebody else to celebrate an event of or to

compensate for an achievement done by the receiver. For example, a middle-aged man participated in the survey told that he had got a necktie from his beloved daughter for the first time in his life. He loved the product just because it was presented by his daughter for the first time.

- **Intrinsic meaning (EE2)** refers satisfaction experienced because of product (or service)-related episode. This includes monumental experiences such as first-time experience, however it is still from a single accident in the past. While extrinsic meaning is delivered by others, intrinsic meaning is made by the user himself or herself. In the survey, a respondent mentioned his Daewoo car as his favorite product, which had been owned at the first time in his life.
- **Retrospective experience (EE3)** tells the cases resulting from a series of anamnestic experiences related to users' product or service, or the users' product or service experience during a particular period. For example, one respondent said he likes Yakima's speaker because it is quite old and makes crackling sound as like as radio used in his younger days.
- **Troubleshooter (EE4)** is based on experience aroused when products or services help users physically or psychologically solve problems which

IE1 Geforce's Titan

IE2 a Gas boiler

IE3 a Coffee brewer

IE4 a Coffee machine

Figure 5. Examples of instrumental experience sub-categories.

EE1 a Necktie

EE2 Daewoo, a car

EE3 Yakima's speaker

EE4 a Bidet

Figure 6. Examples of episodic experience sub-categories.

they had experienced. For instance, a respondent was able to resolve her defecation problem by using a bidet and the product became her favorite product in her daily life.

made up with organically cultivated materials standing for environmental sustainability. A respondent also mentioned Aoyama Flower Market flower scissors as her most favorite because the scissors stands for small relax between our busy daily lives.

Value Experience (see examples in Figure 7)

Symbolic Experience (see examples in Figure 8)

- **Self-improvement (VE1)** refers to positive user experience originating from personal or psychological growth such as improvement of ability, self-administration, self-realization, motivation or satisfying desires through the usage of product or service. According to the survey result, a candle warmer, for example, was mentioned as most favorite product because it helped her to keep improving herself mentally.
- **Personal value (VE2)** means experience made when a product or a service reflects personally pursued ideas or values well. Personal value represents personal preference through products or services. It includes uniqueness, early-adoption, communication, safety and so on. For instance, a male respondent selected a unique hip sack as his favorite because it was not a common style bag everyone carries.
- **Common benefit (VE3)** means personally accepted values commonly shared in the society, such as social norms, cultural value, or ideology. Common benefit is usually affected by interests of group or society that the person belongs to. Cosmetic product called Artistry was one of most favorite products in the survey. She loved it because it was

- **Social recognition (SyE1)** means that a product user wants the user or his/her society to be considered as having distinguished characteristics from others by using product(s) of specific brand. A respondent using a backpack, answered that she thought as if she became a person to have a good sense of design by carrying the bag.
- **Brand image/identity (SyE2)** refers to experience in relation to impression, aura, or symbolic image which a brand aims to deliver and it is something to be commonly recognized in a society. A female respondent said she liked Nike's running shoes because it represents young, energetic and urban health lifestyle.
- **Brand credibility (SyE3)** means experience resulting from trust and confidence that a brand implies while a user experiences the brand direct or indirectly. Multiple numbers of respondents said they support and trust Apple's iPhone because the brand Apple has strong brand credibility.
- **Sense of belonging (SyE4)** refers to experience made when a user feels homogeneity and solidarity by using the same kind of product or

VE1 a Candle warmer

VE2 GFLAT's hip sack

VE3 Artistry(cosmetics)

VE3 Flower scissors

Figure 7. Examples of value experience sub-categories.

Figure 8. Examples of symbolic experience sub-categories.

Figure 9. Positive user experience trend throughout product types.

service with others. A pair of Air Jordan shoes was mentioned as favorite product in the survey. The reason of liking the product was that they are all numbered and it provides the user with connection between people who wear the shoes.

Evaluation of each positive user experience attribute by product type

In all product types but home/decorations and stationaries instrumental experience had the highest

score among user experience attributes (Table 2). Sensory experience was secondly important attribute in those product types but this was not the case in some categories such as home appliances and service. Interestingly, respondents gave the highest score to sensory experience in case of home/decoration category. The other experiences did not show a particular pattern throughout product types (Figure 9). In case of episodic experience, it was most important in stationaries/hobbies category. The experience was

Table 2. Mean values of each user experience attribute according to product type.

Product type	N	Sensory Experience	Instrumental Experience	Episodic Experience	Value Experience	Symbolic Experience
Consumer electronics	28	4.00	4.50	2.79	2.96	3.50
Cosmetics/beauty	16	4.00	4.06	3.19	3.00	3.19
Sports	8	4.13	4.38	3.50	3.50	3.75
Computer accessories	8	3.38	4.75	2.88	3.13	2.75
Home appliances	7	3.57	4.14	3.57	3.71	3.14
Home/decorations	6	4.17	4.00	3.50	2.83	2.33
Stationaries	5	3.80	3.80	4.80	2.80	3.20
Service	17	3.00	4.47	2.76	3.47	2.59

least important in consumer electronics/electronic accessories and sports categories and almost least in cosmetics, computer-related products and service categories. Value experience was not highly scored throughout product types except for home appliances and service categories. Finally, symbolic experience also was not considered as an important attribute to explain why the respondents were fond of their product or service.

Most important attribute in positive user experience

Among 102 products and services, instrumental experience was most frequently mentioned as the most important positive user experience attribute. Sensory experience (19.6%) was secondly ranked, which was followed by symbolic (9.8%) and episodic (9.8%) experiences. value (2.94%) experience was least mentioned (Figure 10).

The usage stage and positive user experience attributes

Any products and services that the respondents mentioned as the most favorite one were not on the first stage of usage. From stage 2 to 5, there were 4, 21, 69, and 8 cases, and the scores of each attribute were averaged within the stage groups. User experience attributes showed patterns throughout the stage of usage (Figure 11). Instrumental experience had generally higher scores than the other throughout all the stages of usage. Sensory experience and value experience showed their lowest scores at stage 5. On the contrary, episodic experience could be considered as a main contributor at the stage, and it showed much higher score than any other stages' scores. In case of symbolic experience, it showed relatively higher score at 'First use' and 'Ongoing use: Phase 1' stages, but it had the lowest score at the stage of 'Discarding or Changing'.

Figure 10. Percentages of the most frequently mentioned attribute of positive user experience.

Discussion and conclusions

Product type and positive user experience

When the respondents were asked about their most favorite product or service, consumer electronics were most frequently mentioned. This might be explained by the phenomenon that consumer electronics have been featured by many novel functions such as music player, camera and fitness aid and at the same time they have been increasingly popular and pervasive to our everyday life. The secondly often mentioned product category was service and cosmetics. A possible explanation of why they became such lovely ones is that the quality of service has been increased as it is an important marketing strategy and people have been more and more exposed to the positive experience from such service. Escaping the period when functionality and performance are important, much attention to personal care has been paid until recently. This seems to lead to more and easier consumption of cosmetic products. Along with the interest, the quality of cosmetics has also been improved probably thanks to technological advance. It could explain why people often mentioned cosmetic

Figure 11. Trend of positive user experience attributes over the stage of product usage.

products as their favorite products. Interestingly, consumer electronics, cosmetics and service are what has been radically improved in terms of quality and diversity recently. This radical improvement in quality and diversity could explain why people love a product or a service. In other words, positive user experience in a product category seems to be made depending on how novel and diverse experiences can be provided with people.

Sub-categories of positive user experience attributes

Five attributes of positive user experience were made on the basis of existing theories and models on user experience. Their definitions were useful to figure out how positive user experience is composed of. However, categorizing a case into one of them was sometimes confusing because positive user experience is an outcome of the interaction between entities such as user, product and context. With clear descriptions of positive user experience, subcategories of positive user experience attributes, it would help design practitioners easily figure out what attribute exactly stands for, on one hand. It could provide them with affluent knowledge of what and how attributes of positive user experience should be taken into consideration.

Evaluation of each positive user experience attribute by product type

Although most of product categories have their highest score in instrumental experience sensory experience and episodic experience were most important in home decoration and stationary categories respectively. Products within the home decoration category include tableware, dishes, book shelves, bedclothes, etc. Because these products are relatively simple-functioned and aesthetic-focused in many cases, sensory experience would be more importantly considered than their functionality. Most of favorite products within stationary category were souvenir from himself/herself or gift from others. Obviously, episodic experience is of importance reminding them of a story or a memory. To products used in open places such as gym and outside home, symbolic experience was also an important attribute next to instrumental and sensory experiences. Value experience is somehow evident only in home appliances and service. Considering that home appliances is closely related to health and energy saving issues, it makes sense that the experience could be as important as instrumental experience. As a representative of services, SNS has been used by many people and stimulates communication between people. Through the service, people feel emotions lacking today such as friendship, respect and intimacy. This can explain why value experience is secondly ranked among five attributes.

Distribution of the most important positive user experience attribute

As the results indicate, both instrumental experience and sensory experience can explain approximately 80% of the reasons why people love a product or a service. Especially, instrumental experience takes more than half of the reasons and this implies the

experience is seriously taken into consideration as a key element throughout product development process. Especially about instrumental experience, the difference may be made by the consumers' memories about achievement. According to the study of Hoch (2002), Instrumental value or goal of consumers tends to be relevant and involving to the consumers, and Huffman and Houston (1993) found consumers' memory improved when the experience was organized around their goal. In other words, instrumental attributes could be easily perceived by the consumers than others.

The usage stage and positive user experience attributes

We found out that dominant attributes of positive user experience differ according to the stage of product usage. Even though the scores for each usage stage are not always based on the same types of product, it is meaningful to compare tendencies between usage stages in terms of UX. A product usage stage at which a certain attribute works relatively stronger than the others in positive user experience could be indirectly anticipated by comparing these tendencies. When people purchase or own a product or a service, its instrumental, sensory, value and symbolic attributes are already considered in the phase. Except for instrumental experience (hard to depreciate due to the ultimate goal to have it), the importance of those experiences tend to decrease over time because they are characterized as momentary experience which does not last long. As episodic experience is something to be accumulated during the usage period, it is the only experience to tend to increase over time. In many cases, people still own the product because of their episodic experience with the product or service although the product had been already out of use. This finding is in line with the study of Karapanos (2010). According to him, as time goes by familiarity (stimulation and learnability), functional dependency and emotional attachment are key attributes of product experience in order across the usage of the product.

The study redefined five attributes of positive user experience and empirically identified the validity of the taxonomy with our everyday products and services. In addition to that, it revealed how attributes of positive user experience are in relation to product types. Considering that most of studies in user experience have dealt with overall experience regardless of usage period, the finding that positive user experience is dependent upon time is meaningful. Nonetheless, the study has some limitations. The sample could make the results biased because half of the respondents was students. It could work as the other limitation that they were from South Korea considering cultural background influences positive user experience and favorite products or services. Therefore, the limitations should be carefully taken into account for a further study.

Acknowledgements

We thank UNIST undergraduate students who helped collect the data of the study, Soyeon Lee, Jeong-cheol Heo, and Sorin Kim. This work was supported by the

'Promotion of Special Design-Technology Convergence Graduate School' of the Korea Institute of Design Promotion with a grant from the Ministry of the Trade, Industry & Energy, Republic of Korea. (N0001436)

References

Cathy, M. (2014). Designing Out of Box and First Time User Experiences to Delight Your Customers. Retrieved from https://www.hcde.washington.edu/files/moya_ppt_creating_great_first_impressions.pdf

Desmet, P., & Hekkert, P. (2007). Framework of product experience. *International Journal of Design*, 1(1), 57–66. <http://doi.org/10.1162/074793602320827406>

Hassenzahl, M. (2003). CHAPTER 3 - THE THING AND I: UNDERSTANDING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN USER AND PRODUCT. *Funology*, 3, 31–42. http://doi.org/10.1007/1-4020-2967-5_4

Hassenzahl, M. (2008). User experience (UX): Towards an experiential perspective on product quality. *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference of the Association Francophone d'Interaction Homme-Machine on - IHM '08*, 11–15. <http://doi.org/10.1145/1512714.1512717>

Hassenzahl, M., & Tractinsky, N. (2006). User experience - a research agenda. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 25(2), 91–97. <http://doi.org/10.1080/01449290500330331>

Hassenzahl, M., & Ullrich, D. (2007). To do or not to do: Differences in user experience and retrospective judgments depending on the presence or absence of instrumental goals. *Interacting with Computers*, 19(4), 429–437. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.intcom.2007.05.001>

Hoch, S. J. (2002). Product Experience Is Seductive. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 29(3), 448–454. <http://doi.org/10.1086/344422>

Huffman, C., & Houston, M. J. (1993). Goal-Oriented Experiences and the Development of Knowledge. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 20(2), 190. <http://doi.org/10.1086/209343>

ISO. (2010). No Title. In *ISO 9241-210: Ergonomics of human-system interaction — Part 210: Human-centred design for interactive systems*.

Jordan, P. W. (1999). *Pleasure with products: Human factors for body, mind and soul. Human factors in product design: Current practice and future trends*.

Karapanos, E., Zimmerman, J., Forlizzi, J., & Martens, J.-B. (2010). Measuring the Dynamics of Remembered Experience Over Time. *Interacting with Computers*, 22(5), 328–335. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.intcom.2010.04.003>

Kim, C. (2014). User characteristics and behaviour in operating annoying electronic products. *International Journal of Design*, 8(1), 93–108.

Kim, C., & Christiaans, H. (2012). "Soft" usability problems with consumer electronics: the interaction between user characteristics and usability. *J. of Design Research*, 10(3), 223. <http://doi.org/10.1504/JDR.2012.047938>

Kramer, J., Noronha, S., & Vergo, J. (2000). A user-centered design approach to personalization. *Communications of the ACM*, 43(8), 45–48. <http://doi.org/10.1145/345124.345139>

Lew, R. (2011). User studies: Opportunities and limitations. *ASIALEX2011 Proceedings. Lexicography: Theoretical and Practical Perspectives*, 7–16. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10593/1253>

Low, E. (2006). Designing Product Character : Strategy to Evaluate Product Preference. In *Design Research Society* (pp. 1–7).

Moggridge, B., & Atkinson, B. (2007). *Designing interactions* (Vol. 14). MIT press Cambridge.

Rafaeli, A., & Vilnai-Yavetz, I. (2004). Instrumentality, aesthetics and symbolism of physical artifacts as triggers of emotion. *Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science*, 5(1), 91–112. <http://doi.org/10.1080/1463922031000086735>

Spinuzzi, C. (2005). The Methodology of Participatory Design. *Technical Communication*, 52(2), 163–174. Retrieved from <http://www.ingentaconnect.com/content/stc/tc/2005/00000052/00000002/art00005>

von Wilamowitz Moellendorff, M., Hassenzahl, M., Platz, a, & Wilamowitz-Moellendorff, M. Von. (2006). Dynamics of user experience: How the perceived quality of mobile phones changes over time. *User Experience - Towards a Unified View, Workshop at the 4th Nordic Conference on Human-Computer Interaction*, (JANUARY 2006), 74–78.

Wright, P., & McCarthy, J. (2010). *Experience-Centered Design: Designers, Users, and Communities in Dialogue. Synthesis Lectures on Human-Centered Informatics* (Vol. 3). <http://doi.org/10.2200/S00229ED1V01Y201003HCI009>